

Development of a Low Cost Poultry Egg Incubation System

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Abstract:

The egg incubator is a device that allows poultry breeders to generate more chicks without the mother hen. To do this, the system was automated using an Arduino microcontroller. The DHT11 sensor is at the core of the temperature and humidity monitoring system, and the system's status is presented on the LCD at regular intervals. The results reveal that the system was able to automatically maintain the temperature within the prescribed range, allowing the eggs to hatch after 21 days.

Keywords: *Egg incubator, Agriculture, Food sustainability, Arduino UNO, Sustainable Development Goals.*

Introduction

Food is one of the fundamental necessities that people require, ranking first, followed by clothing and shelter, which rank third. Human beings require what they eat to be nutritionally balanced with components of carbohydrates, protein, fats, oils, minerals, etc. There are numerous ways to obtain carbohydrates from tuber crops and other plants, which are easily assessed even in many of the world's poorest regions. Proteins, which are very important for healthy growth, can be obtained from both plants and animals. However, when it comes to animal protein, significant focus is put on limiting the intake of red meat derived from cows, sheep, and other ruminant animals, whereas eating white meat is promoted since it has fewer health hazards than red meat. These white meats come from poultry species, including chickens, turkeys, guinea fowls etc. The growth in the human population has resulted in a significant increase in demand for white meat, making it impossible for chicken

producers to supply this need via natural egg hatching. As a result, there is a need for artificial methods of hatching poultry products and white meat sources.

In recent decades, meat output has reached historically high levels as demand for animal protein products has increased. Since 1961, the global output of broiler meat has expanded more than eightfold. In 2010, the world produced 55.3 billion chicks, yielding 86.1 million tons of chicken meat (FAOSTAT, 2011). Since 1990, the price of chicken meat has fluctuated between 800 and 1000 USD/ton, with the exception of 1999 and 2004, when it fell below 600 USD/ton (FAO, 2010). The demand for poultry products such as eggs, meat, and birds is increasing on a daily basis, and the globe cannot rely entirely on natural incubation methods, necessitating the use of artificial incubators (Adetola *et al.*, 2019).

The United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) refer to a set of 17 goals which serves as a target of member nations to be achieved by the year 2030. Nigeria became

a member of the UN on 7th October 1960 after gaining her independence status from the British on the 1st of October, 1960. The goals were set at a meeting in 2015. The SDG goals include

“1. No poverty; 2. Zero hunger; 3. Good health and well-being; 4. Quality education; 5. Gender equality; 6. Clean water and sanitation; 7. Affordable and clean energy; 8. Decent work and economic growth; 9. Industry, innovation and agriculture; 10. Reduced inequality; 11. Sustainable cities and communities; 12. Responsible consumption and production; 13. Climate action; 14. Life below water; 15. Life on land; 16. Peace, justice and strong institution; 17. Partnerships for the goals.” (UNDP, 2024)

Attainment of the 17 SDGs has attracted serious research interests in member states since they were established.

Using an incubator to hatch has three primary advantages over broody hens: chicks are hatched whenever there is a demand for them, rather than having to wait for hens to become broody; a large number of eggs can be hatched at once; and an incubator is required if the poultry breeder wishes to sell baby chicks (Adegbulugbe *et al.*, 2013).

An incubator is a device that allows poultry breeders to generate chicks without a mother hen. It is one of the quickest and easiest techniques to hatch chicks from eggs. The most essential distinction between natural and artificial incubation is that the natural parent warms the egg via touch rather than enclosing it with warm air.

Chicken eggs spend around a day in the tract and 21 days in incubation before being brooded by the mother hen. Egg incubation is the process by which eggs from egg-laying (oviparous) animals grow embryos inside them after their production and ovipositional discharge. Eggs hatch under steady and suitable environmental circumstances. The incubation environment is the most critical factor that influences egg hatchability. Temperature, humidity, ventilation, and turning during incubation have a major impact on the hatchability of viable eggs and chick quality (Harb *et al.*, 2010). Temperature

and humidity are two of the most important elements affecting the hatchability of viable eggs. These characteristics were carefully considered while designing the incubator.

Incubators are machines used to hatch chicken products. The successful incubation of poultry eggs to maturity is dependent on the effective regulation of two parameters: temperature and relative humidity. To be able to regulate these characteristics, first and foremost, they must be measurable. The ideal temperature range for chicken egg incubation is 37–38.5°C (Okpagu & Nwosu, 2016; Radhakrishnan, 2014). While the relative humidity value ranges between 50% and 75%, the DHT11 sensor reads both ambient temperature and ambient relative humidity readings. The DHT11 sensor is a low-cost and low-power-consuming digital signal calibration sensor used to measure the temperature and humidity in the atmosphere. Capacitive polymer elements make it up (Kodali & Valdas, 2018; Puspitasari, Setijadi & Affandi, 2020; Setiawan, Hariyono & Ramelan, 2022; Firmansyah *et al.*, 2022; Niam & Sungkar, 2024; Adiono, 2018). It can detect temperatures from 0 to 50 °C and humidity levels from 20 to 90%. This study made use of an embedded system. An embedded system is a computing system composed of both software and computer hardware that is designed for one purpose or function, which it is expected to perform with a high degree of reliability and with minimal user intervention (Subero, 2021; Talukdar, Mehta, & Gajjar, 2019; Winarno *et al.*, 2022). There are several kinds of embedded systems, including real-time embedded systems and networked embedded systems (Subero, 2021; Marwedel, 2021; Kim & Kim, 2023; Abdelwahab, 2022; Aloseel, Shaw & Khan, 2020; Aloseel *et al.*, 2020; Woo, 2021; Ikuabe *et al.*, 2023; Sonko *et al.*, 2024). In this study, we use a real-time embedded system because we need it to react immediately to sensor inputs. Embedded systems are made up of microcontrollers and hardware. A microcontroller is a self-contained programmable device in a single integrated circuit that has input/output capabilities, provides local computational resources to a number of electrical devices, and can make

decisions based on the current program (Ionita, 2020; Barrett & Pack, 2019; Idris, Irdayanti, & Ramlee, 2024; Yantidewi *et al.*, 2021). An Arduino microcontroller is a low-cost embedded system that may be used to operate linked hardware depending on sensor readings and the software stored in it (Iyen *et al.*, 2020; Akeredolu *et al.*, 2017; Iyen, C., Ayomanor, & Orseer, 2024; Ja'afaru *et al.*, 2018; Ayomanor *et al.*, 2024). It is an open-source embedded system electronics platform made up of memory, processors, and peripherals. It is a simple hardware and software system that can be programmed for any given purpose and used for rapid prototyping of electronics projects (Aba *et al.*, 2021; Saini *et al.*, 2023; Suraj *et al.*, 2019; Chand & Khosla, 2022). Poultry egg incubation is the process of hatching eggs using either a broody hen or an incubator machine (Adame & Ameha, 2023). Egg incubation is one of the major categories of contemporary chicken production (Domatskiy, 2019). Egg incubation is the process of developing the egg embryo until hatching is accomplished (Niranjan *et al.*, 2021). According to Szoiga and Bondric (2020), egg incubation is the most effective way to produce protein for human consumption. It is the most essential technical connection in big poultry farms (Duvanov *et al.*, 2021), as well as a technology that allows breeders to generate chicks from eggs utilizing engineering approaches (Junaidi *et al.*, 2021). It is the process by which eggs are kept warm at specified temperatures and humidity in order to develop and hatch the embryo after a certain number of days (Fredrick *et al.*, 2021).

Many studies have been conducted using the Arduino microcontroller and embedded systems to achieve sustainable development goals. For example, Nugraha and Priyambodo (2021) used the Arduino microcontroller to create a hydro-organic monitoring system to automatically monitor plant watering, which was used to improve rice yield and contribute to the achievement of SDG goal 2: zero hunger. Srinivasan *et al.* (2013) used the Arduino microcontroller to regulate power supply to information technology-based educational facilities for rural inhabitants in India, adding to

research on sustainable development through education. Nugraha and Priyambodo (2020) utilized the Arduino microcontroller to create a control system for detecting turbidity levels in catfish ponds, contributing to SDG No. 9: industry, innovation, and infrastructure. Sekhar *et al.* (2023) built an IOT-based Arduino project that is used to monitor water quality. Agilah *et al.* (2021) created a smart trash disposal system utilizing the Arduino controller and a variety of sensors.

Though much work has been done using an Arduino to implement poultry egg incubation systems (Bari, Hossain & Khan, 2021; Szolga & Bondric, 2020; Fredrick *et al.*, 2021; Kyeremeh & Peprah, 2017; Yendri, Yolanda & Sibaraani, 2021), the goal of this research is to develop a low-cost system based on locally available resources for training and educational purposes, and the knowledge gained can be applied to other microcontroller-based projects. This research work will assist in attaining SDG goals 2 and 4.

Method and Design

The incubator is a thermal system that is expected to provide the amount of heat required to get a great percentage hatchability of any breed of eggs incubated in it with high energy efficiency and at a cheap cost. The materials for the construction of the incubator are listed below,

1. Arduino microcontroller
2. Heat and humidity sensor (DHT11)
3. Incandescent bulb(100W)
4. LCD (16*2)
5. Relays (5V, 10A)
6. Resistors (10K Ω Var, 330 Ω)
7. Diodes
8. Power circuit (220V/5V)
9. Transistors
10. Fans, 5V 2A

The system was constructed from local materials and simple electronic components to make it less expensive which is advantageous for household use.

The artificial incubator is designed with the Arduino as the center, controlling all the other components. The flow chart of the work is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the Project

Mechanical Design

The mechanical structure was constructed using wood which is a poor conductor of heat and hence heat loss is minimal. Within, is a 100watt bulb that serves as the heat source, and on the two opposite sides, is the fan which cools the eggs and also helps in the circulation of air for equal distribution of heat. Also, holes were bored in the box for ventilation. The chamber has a dimension of 30cm*30cm*20.3cm

Electronic Design

The circuit is divided into two; the Temperature control unit and the power supply unit. The block diagram is shown in figure 2 and the circuit diagram is shown in figure 3.

Figure 2. Block Diagram of the Incubator System

Figure 3. Circuit Diagram of Incubator System

Software Design

The software design process has to do with programming the Arduino microcontroller. Arduino is easy to program and has functionalities that make it easy for automated control. Special header files such as the DHT11 header and LCD header, are needed in Programming the Arduino microcontroller as an egg incubator controller. The Arduino serves as the brain of the circuit controlling it. The DHT11 sensor, reads the temperature and humidity in the incubator, sending the information to the Arduino. The Arduino in turn prints the information on the LCD. The temperature range of the incubator is 37°C - 39°C . The 100watt bulb is ON until the temperature within the incubator is reaches 39°C . At maximum temperature (39°C), the fans are ON and the bulb is OFF until the temperature steadily drops to the minimum (37°C). At minimum temperature (37°C), the fans are OFF while the bulb is ON. The

ON/OFF of the bulb and fans is controlled by the Arduino.

Result / Discussion

The components needed were first tested and the connection was done on a breadboard, to avoid errors in the circuit. Which were later transferred to a Vero-board and soldered with minimum heat to avoid damage to components. After the soldering, the circuit was tested and found to work appropriately, with the result shown in figure 5.

Due to the fluctuations in the ambient temperature, the temperature within the system also vary simultaneously. From the temperature graph, it can be noted that the temperature was steadily raised from an ambient temperature of 33°C to 38°C for the first 1hour. There was not much change observed in the system afterward, which indicates that the wood used did well in minimizing the heat loss.

Figure 4. Assembling of the System

Figure 5. Temperature-Time Graph of the First 24 Hours

Conclusion

The work began with an investigation into the necessary factors affecting incubation and thereby materials were selected. The wood used preserves heat well, hence loss is minimal. The incubator is portable, easy to maintain. It was developed majorly from local materials and Arduino was used as the microcontroller, a 100watt bulb as the heat source, and also fans, for air circulation.

The condition inside the incubator per time is displayed by the LCD (16*2). There is no need for regular intervention of the operator or personnel in charge since the system is automated and controlled by the Arduino, maintaining the conditions necessary (as coded).

Recommendation

Since the world is getting more digital, smart incubators can be developed with a monitoring system that is able to send messages to the personnel in charge with information about its state.

References

- Aba, E. N., Olugboji, O. A., Nasir, A., Olutoye, M. A., & Adedipe, O. (2021). Petroleum pipeline monitoring using an internet of things (IoT) platform. *SN Applied Sciences*, 3, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-021-04225-z>
- Abdelwahab, B. M. (2022, September). Embedded Systems and Vehicle Networks. In *The International Undergraduate Research Conference* (Vol. 6, No. 6, pp. 1-6). The Military Technical College. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/1086519.1086522>
- Adame, M.M., & Ameha, N. (2023). Review on Egg Handling and Management of Incubation and Hatchery Environment. *Asian Journal of Biological Sciences*, 16(4), 474-484. <https://doi.org/10.3923/ajbs.2023.474.484>
- Adegbulugbe, T. A., Atere, A. O., & Fasanmi, O. G. (2013). Development of an automatic electric egg incubator. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 4(9), 914-918.
- Adetola S.O, Adegbite A.S, Adewale K.A and Ibiwoye O.S (2019). Design, construction and testing of a kerosene powered multi bird-egg incubator. *LAUTECH Journal of Civil and Environmental Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.36108/laujoces%2F9102%2F20%280210%29>
- Adiono, T., Fathany, M. Y., Fuada, S., Purwanda, I. G., & Anindya, S. F. (2018, April). A portable node of humidity and temperature sensor for indoor environment monitoring. In *2018 3rd International Conference on Intelligent Green Building and Smart Grid (IGBSG)* (pp. 1-5). IEEE. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/IGBSG.2018.8393575>
- Akeredolu, J. B., Wansah, J. F., Omega, H. E., Iseh, A. J., Ocheje, A. J., & Iyen, C. (2017). Development of a low cost automated sliding door. *FUW Trends in Science Technology Journal*, 2(1), 281-289.
- Aloseel, A., He, H., Shaw, C., & Khan, M. A. (2020). Analytical review of cybersecurity for embedded systems. *IEEE Access*, 9, 961-982. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3045972>
- Aqilah, R. M., Elfahmi, A. S., Fariza, R., Oktalia, R. D., & Wahyudi, B. T. (2021, December). Smart Trash Can: Innovation of Automatic Trash Can with Arduino Uno-Based as an Effort to Support Global Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) Action. In *International Conference on Science and Engineering (ICSE-UIN-SUKA 2021)* (pp. 203-209). Atlantis Press.
- Ayomanor B., Liambee A., Atanda J. S., Jeremiah J. J., Oluwasegun A., & Iyen C. (2024). Implementation of Home Automation System Using GSM Module and Arduino Microcontroller. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 14(5), 150-159
- Bari, M. A., Hossain, M. J., & Khan, M. M. (2021, December). Development of Smart Egg Incubator. In *2021 IEEE 12th Annual Ubiquitous Computing, Electronics & Mobile Communication*

Conference (UEMCON) (pp. 0527-0533). IEEE. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/UEMCON53757.2021.9666653>

Barrett, S. F., & Pack, D. J. (2019). Introduction to Microcontroller Technology. In *Microcontroller Programming and Interfacing Texas Instruments MSP430 Part I* (pp. 1-24). Cham: Springer International Publishing.

Chand, K., & Khosla, A. (2022). MATLAB-Based Real-Time Data Acquisition Tool for Multimodal Biofeedback and Arduino-Based Instruments: Arduino Firmata Data Acquisition (AfDaq). *Journal of Information Technology Research (JITR)*, 15(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.4018/JITR.299922>

Domatskiy, V. N. (2019). Differentiated incubation of chicken eggs. *Bulgarian Journal of Agricultural Science*, 25.

Duvanov, E. S., Kudinov, Y. I., Pashchenko, F. F., & Duvanova, V. S. (2021, November). Analysis of the Technological Process of Egg Incubation and Formulation of the Control Problem. In *2021 3rd International Conference on Control Systems, Mathematical Modeling, Automation and Energy Efficiency (SUMMA)* (pp. 769-773). IEEE.

FAO (2010) *Agribusiness handbook: Poultry meat and eggs*. Rome, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.

FAOSTAT (2011) *Chicken meat production*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Online Database. Accessed on 22/12/2010

Firmansyah, O., Ridwan, A. M., Hamidi, E. A. Z., & Fitriani, P. D. (2022, July). Prototype of Temperature and Humidity Control System for Oyster Mushroom Cultivation Using Arduino Uno Based on The Internet of Things. In *2022 8th International Conference on Wireless and Telematics (ICWT)* (pp. 1-4). IEEE. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/ICWT55831.2022.9935358>

Fredrick, O. M., Umar, U. T., Edmund, A. N., & Ohunene, Z. Z. (2021). Design and Implementation of a Remotely Monitored Smart

Egg Incubator. *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, 12, 1009-1017.

Harb, S. K., Y. A. Habbib, A. M. Kassem, And A. El Raies, (2010) Energy Consumption aor Poultry Egg Incubator to Suit Small Farmer. *Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 88, 193-210.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.21608/ejar.2010.180260>

Idris, M. R., Irdyanti, M. N., & Ramlee, M. (2024, March). A review of microcontroller design in future industrial revolution. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2750, No. 1). AIP Publishing.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/5.0041705>

Ikuabe, M., Aigbavboa, C., Oke, A., & Aghimien, D. (2023, October). A Scientometric Review of Present and Future Trends of Embedded Systems in the Built Environment. In *Proceedings of the Future Technologies Conference* (pp. 489-499). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland. http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-47448-4_36

Ionita, A. C. (2020). Headless Internet of Things Devices That Provide User Interface Models. *Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brasov. Series I-Engineering Sciences*, 35-42. <https://doi.org/10.31926/but.ens.2020.13.62.1.5>

Iyen, C., Ayomanor, B., & Orseer, D. (2024). Implementation of Bluetooth Enabled Home Automation System. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(2), 310-318. <https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2%282%29.27>

Iyen, C., Ayomanor, B., Orume, A., Saleh, S., Jaafaru, S., & Akeredolu, B. J. (2020). Design and construction of a rain detector with an alarm system. *FUW Trends in Science Technology Journal*, 5(3), 686-690.

Ja'afaru, S., Dogara, M. D., Isaac, H. D., Gyuk, P. M., & Iyen, C. (2018). Comparison between a constructed Arduino based system and Keithley Sourcemeter 2400 on some Electronics Devices. *Science World Journal*, 13(2), 55-57. <https://doi.org/10.4314/SWJ.V13I2>

- Junaidi, A., Adhinata, F. D., Iskandar, A. R., & Lasama, J. (2022, June). Image classification for egg incubator using transfer learning VGG16 and InceptionV3. In *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Electronics, Biomedical Engineering, and Health Informatics: ICEBEHI 2021, 3-4 November, Surabaya, Indonesia* (pp. 85-95). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/COMNETSAT53002.2021.9530826>
- Junaidi, A., Lasama, J., Adhinata, F. D., & Iskandar, A. R. (2021, July). Image classification for EGG incubator using transfer learning of VGG16 and VGG19. In *2021 IEEE International Conference on Communication, Networks and Satellite (COMNETSAT)* (pp. 324-328). IEEE. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/COMNETSAT53002.2021.9530826>
- Kim, J., & Kim, S. (2023). Hardware accelerators in embedded systems. In *Artificial Intelligence and Hardware Accelerators* (pp. 167-181). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Kodali, R. K., & Valdas, A. (2018, August). Mqtt based monitoring system for urban farmers using esp32 and raspberry pi. In *2018 Second International Conference on Green Computing and Internet of Things (ICGCIoT)* (pp. 395-398). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICGCIOT.2018.8752995>
- Kyeremeh, F., & Pephrah, F. (2017). Design and Construction of an Arduino Microcontroller-based EGG Incubator. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 168(1), 15-23. <https://doi.org/10.5120/IJCA2017914261>
- Marwedel, P. (2021). *Embedded system design: embedded systems foundations of cyber-physical systems, and the internet of things* (p. 433). Springer Nature.
- Niam, B., & Sungkar, M. S. (2024, April). Development of electronic laboratory temperature and humidity detection using fuzzy logic and mysql database methods. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 3070, No. 1). AIP Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0199168>
- Niranjan, L., Venkatesan, C., Suhas, A. R., Satheeskumaran, S., & Nawaz, S. A. (2021). Design and implementation of chicken egg incubator for hatching using IoT. *International Journal of Computational Science and Engineering*, 24(4), 363-372. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1504/IJCSE.2021.10039967>
- Nugraha, A. T., & Priyambodo, D. (2020). Design of pond water turbidity monitoring system in arduino-based catfish cultivation to support sustainable development goals 2030 No. 9 industry, innovation, and infrastructure. *Journal of Electronics, Electromedical Engineering, and Medical Informatics*, 2(3), 119-124. <http://dx.doi.org/10.35882/jecemi.v2i3.6>
- Nugraha, A. T., & Priyambodo, D. (2021). Design of a monitoring system for hydroganics based on arduino uno R3 to realize sustainable development goals number 2 zero hunger. *Journal of Electronics, Electromedical Engineering, and Medical Informatics*, 3(1), 50-56. <https://doi.org/10.35882/JEEEMI.V3I1.8>
- Okonkwo, W. I., & Chukwuezie, O. C. (2012). Characterization of a photovoltaic powered poultry egg incubator. In *4th International Conference on Agriculture and Animal Science. Singapore. doi* (Vol. 10).
- Okpagu, P. E., & Nwosu, A. W. (2016). Development and temperature control of smart egg incubator system for various types of egg. *European Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 4(2).
- Puspitasari, W., Setijadi, E., & Affandi, A. (2020, July). Design of Sensor Node for Greenhouse Real-Time Monitoring System. In *2020 International Seminar on Intelligent Technology and Its Applications (ISITIA)* (pp. 71-76). IEEE. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/ISITIA49792.2020.9163751>
- Radhakrishnan, K., Jose, N., Sanjay, S. G., Cherian, T., & Vishnu, K. R. (2014). Design and implementation of a fully automated egg incubator. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Electrical, Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering*, 3(2), 2056-5860.
- Saini, D. K. J. B., Ahammad, S. H., Das, P., Bhatt, A., Malusare, P., & Pande, S. D. (2023, September). Grading of Fruit Ripeness Using

Arduino in IoT. In *2023 International Conference on Sustainable Emerging Innovations in Engineering and Technology (ICSEIET)* (pp. 184-188). IEEE. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/ICSEIET58677.2023.10303541>

Santoso, A., Arif, I., Masduki, M., & Rachmanto, R. (2021). IIS Room Temperature Monitoring at Juanda Airport with Android Iot Based Using Message Queue Telemetry Transport Protocol. *European Scholar Journal*, 2(12), 88-93.

Sekhar, K. C., Venkatesh, B., Reddy, K. S., Giridhar, G., Nithin, K., & Eshwar, K. (2023). IoT-based Realtime Water Quality Management System using Arduino Microcontroller. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, 14(2), 783-792. <https://doi.org/10.17762/turcomat.v14i2.13734>

Setiawan, G. A., Hariyono, J., & Ramelan, A. (2022). Technology Design to Improve Plant Quality with IoT-Based Plant Temperature and Humidity Monitoring System. *Journal of Electrical, Electronic, Information, and Communication Technology*, 4(2), 61-66. <https://doi.org/10.20961/jeeict.4.2.65902>

Sonko, S., Daudu, C. D., Osasona, F., Monebi, A. M., Etukudoh, E. A., & Atadoga, A. (2024). The evolution of embedded systems in automotive industry: A global review. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 21(2), 096-104. <http://dx.doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.21.2.0420>

Srinivasan, M., AJ, A. V., Victor, A. N., Narayanan, M., SP, S. R., & Vijayaraghavan, V. (2013, October). GreenEduComp: Low cost green computing system for education in Rural India: A scheme for sustainable development through education. In *2013 IEEE Global Humanitarian Technology Conference (GHTC)* (pp. 102-107). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/GHTC.2013.6713663>

Subero, A. (2021). Embedded systems overview. In *Programming Microcontrollers with Python: Experience the Power of Embedded Python* (pp. 77-105). Berkeley, CA: Apress.

Subero, A. (2021). Embedded systems overview. In *Programming Microcontrollers with Python: Experience the Power of Embedded Python* (pp. 77-105). Berkeley, CA: Apress.

Suraj, D.M., Prasad, V.A., Lokesh, S., Hebbale, S.G., & Salis, V.E. (2019). Obstacle Detection for the Visually Impaired Using Arduino. *2019 3rd International Conference on Trends in Electronics and Informatics (ICOEI)*, 260-265. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICOEI.2019.8862635>

Szolga, L. A., & Bondric, A. (2020, October). Smart System for Incubating Eggs. In *2020 IEEE 26th International Symposium for Design and Technology in Electronic Packaging (SIITME)* (pp. 260-264). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SIITME50350.2020.9292305>

Talukdar, J., Mehta, B., & Gajjar, S. (2019). Computational Intelligence in Embedded System Design: A Review. *Information and Communication Technology for Intelligent Systems: Proceedings of ICTIS 2018, Volume 1*, 473-484.

UNDP, (2024). What are the Sustainable Development Goals? United Nations Development Program. Retrieved from <https://www.undp.org/sustainable-development-goals>

Winarno, I., Barakbah, A., Pramadihanto, D., Sesulihatien, W. T., Harsono, T., Dewantara, B. S. B., ... & Susanti, P. (2022). Embedded system training based on Arduino to improve software programming knowledge for vocational students. *Abdimas: Jurnal Pengabdian Masyarakat Universitas Merdeka Malang*, 7(4), 748-758. <http://dx.doi.org/10.26905/abdimas.v7i4.8039>

Woo, L. L. (2021). Anomalous Behaviour in Embedded Systems. *Hardware Supply Chain Security: Threat Modelling, Emerging Attacks and Countermeasures*, 129-145.

Yantidewi, M., Jatmiko*, B., Suchayo, I., Kholiq, A.A., Lestari, N.A., & Deta, U.A. (2021). Getting to Know the Last Five Years Trend on Microcontroller Research: A Bibliometric Analysis. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2110. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2F2110/2F1/2F012006>

Yendri, D., Yolanda, D., & Sibarani, J. F. (2021, November). Temperature and Humidity Control System of Duck Egg Incubator Based on Proportional Integral Derivative. In *2021*

International Conference on Computer Science and Engineering (IC2SE) (Vol. 1, pp. 1-7). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ic2se52832.2021.9792006>